

FAME Legal Framework Documentation

Contributing Organisations

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
FAME CORE Value	4
FAME Onboarding Procedure	6
Purpose and Scope of Application	6
Definitions	6
Onboarding Process	6
1. Authentication & verification	6
2. Assessment	7
3. Voting rules	7
Terms and Conditions for FAME Marketplace	9
Purpose and Scope of Application	9
Definitions	9
1. Access to the Marketplace.....	10
2. Scope of Service.....	10
3. Subscription plan [CURRENTLY FREE TO USE].....	10
4. Functioning of the Marketplace.....	10
5. Acceptable use policy for the Marketplace.....	10
7. Notice and Action Mechanism	11
8. Enhancement of the service	11
9. Representations and warranties	11
10. Right to withdrawal	12
11. Restriction of access	12
Suggested Transaction Terms	12
Purpose and Scope of Application	12
Definitions	13
1. Data assets.....	13
2. Permitted uses	14
3. Prohibited Uses	14
4. Cost and maintenance of Data assets.....	14
5. Privacy And Data Protection.....	15
6. Terms Related to The Use of Derived Material	16
7. Termination Of Contract	16

Executive Summary

This Legal Framework is composed of four core components: (1) FAME Core Values; (2) Onboarding Procedure; (3) Marketplace Terms & Conditions; (4) Suggested Transaction Terms.

Three of these components (*FAME Core Values, Onboarding Procedure, Marketplace Terms & Conditions*) are essential for the proper functioning of the Marketplace. The *Suggested Transaction Terms* serve as a reference, with terms that *may* be used for transaction agreements. They are by no means obligatory for transactions but set a minimum contractual standard for transaction agreements.

1. Core Values

These Core values are a set of principles embodied by the FAME project, and that extend to all its federated members in the marketplace.

2. Onboarding Procedure

Joining the FAME Marketplace requires to undergo an ‘Onboarding procedure’. This is described in the Onboarding Procedure document, which sets certain requirements for the admittance of new applicants. It also provides certain rules and restrictions for the selection of new market participants by the Founding Members.

3. Marketplace Terms & Conditions

Prior to admittance into the Marketplace, an applicant must also accept the *Marketplace terms & conditions*. This document outlines the Marketplace’s service, the limits on the acceptable use of the Marketplace, the Marketplace’s responsibility to maintain the marketplace, and reservation of the Marketplace’s right to moderate content on the platform.

4. Suggested Transaction Terms

The Suggested transaction terms provide a set of non-binding terms that can be used in agreements between buyers and sellers. They should be considered as a minimum contractual standard for transaction agreements.

FAME CORE Value

1. FAME recognises the impact of its activities on all members of society and strives to promote a fair and inclusive space for all its stakeholders.
2. FAME does not condone any form of **unlawful discrimination** and ensures that all its activities and processes do not have any **prejudicial effects** on any individual or groups in society.
3. FAME acknowledges the importance of **environmental sustainability**, designing and maintaining its products and services such that they have minimal impact on the environment.
4. FAME upholds the highest level of **accountability** for all parties involved with the development and operation of its products and services. Furthermore, it will always strive to conduct all its operation in a predictable and reliable fashion.
5. All participants while using the FAME Marketplace's products and services should be able to make their own decisions freely without undue pressures, having been provided with **objective, reliable** and **transparent** information beforehand.
6. Every organisation participating in the FAME Marketplace should be able to **fairly compete** and **innovate** within the parameters of the rules and principles that govern the FAME Marketplace.
7. FAME is committed to respect European laws and values and strives to upholding fundamental rights, including, and in particular, **privacy, data protection, and intellectual property**.
8. FAME acknowledges that some of the services or products offered on the FAME Marketplace might include biases or hidden assumptions. For this reason, FAME strives to **eliminate** such biases and offer an open and equitable environment to all its participants.
9. FAME understands that digital products and services should be designed, produced, and used, in a way that mitigates their negative impact on the **environment** and on **society** and avoids premature obsolescence.
10. FAME acknowledges that the FAME Marketplace and the technology employed should be **safe, secure, and reliable**.
11. FAME strives to serve and benefit all people living in the European Union and empower them to pursue their aspirations, in line with the Competitiveness Agenda set by the European Commission.

12. FAME strives to be used to unite, and not divide, people, and acknowledges that digital transformation should contribute to a fair and **inclusive society** and **economy** in the European Union and beyond.
13. FAME aims to provide digital products and services that everyone can understand and rely on. For this, FAME is committed to promoting digital, data and AI literacy through its learning and education offerings.

FAME Onboarding Procedure

Purpose and Scope of Application

The FAME Onboarding Procedure outlines the procedure for the onboarding of Applicants to the FAME Marketplace. In particular, this document designates certain roles and responsibilities to ensure the orderly assessment of each application.

Definitions

Applicant(s) is an organisation that applies to join the FAME Marketplace and adheres to the FAME Core Values.

Contributing Members are responsible for the assessment and admission of *Applicants* to the *Marketplace*. It may consist of FAME Consortium Members as well as other federated members who can decide to organise themselves into a governance board.

Data assets are data products that are constructed, maintained, and made available on the Marketplace by an *Offeror*. A *User* can discover and use them with respect to the Transaction Terms

FAME Marketplace ('Marketplace') is an information service that establishes a federated marketplace for embedded finance, to promote the valorisation, monetisation and accessibility of data and related services.

FAME Core Values Refers to the FAME CORE Value section.

Offering(s) is any raw data, provided in a structured or unstructured form, AI/ML models and analytical insights, other services, or product that, from time to time, are available on the Marketplace.

Onboarding Process

1. Authentication & verification

- 1.1 In order to become a part of the FAME Marketplace, Applicants are required to go through an onboarding procedure.
- 1.2 An Applicant must submit appropriate verified or verifiable corporate information and documentation, including a signed copy of the FAME Marketplace terms and conditions.

- 1.3 An Applicant who intends to qualify as an Offeror must be in possession of a detailed description of the Data asset(s) they intend to publish in the Marketplace, including any relevant certification.
- 1.4 After the relevant information and documentation has been received, an Applicant will be assessed by the Contributing Members.
- 1.5 The Data assets that an Applicant intends to make available must be secure, function reliably and comply with relevant legal requirements, in addition to the rules stipulated in the FAME Marketplace Terms and Conditions.
- 1.6 Any confidential information provided to FAME during the onboarding process will be kept confidential.
- 1.7 An Applicants' personal data will be processed by the Contributing Member in accordance with FAME's Core Values.

2. Assessment

- 2.1 The Contributing Member will be responsible for assessing the eligibility of Applicants and admitting them into the FAME Marketplace.
- 2.2 A Contributing Member will be responsible for ensuring that the entirety of the selection process is conducted in a transparent and fair manner.
- 2.3 A Contributing Member must ensure that an appropriate amount of consideration is given to each candidate while aligning their assessment with FAME's best interest.
- 2.4 A Contributing Member, in assessing each Applicant, will be accountable to, and must be able to justify their decision on the basis of FAME's Core Values.
- 2.5 To avoid any conflicts of interest, all Contributing Members must disclose any relationship or connection with an Applicant prior to the commencement of an assessment.
- 2.6 The Contributing Members will be responsible for communicating the outcome of a decision to an Applicant within a reasonable amount of time.
- 2.7 All applications, acceptances and rejections of candidates must be documented.
- 2.8 A reject Applicant cannot re-apply prior to a six-month waiting period.
- 2.9 A rejected Applicant cannot re-apply under a different name or to use any approach to circumvent such prohibition.

3. Voting rules

- 3.1 Only Contributing Members can conduct a vote.
- 3.2 The voting system shall be secure.

- 3.3 A vote cannot be transferred to another entity external to FAME.
- 3.4 Voting shall occur within a set time limit.
- 3.5 Each vote needs to be registered for transparency purposes.
- 3.6 Each Contributing Member needs to be notified that their votes have been recorded.
- 3.7 The voting system needs to be easy to access and user friendly.

Terms and Conditions for FAME Marketplace

Purpose and Scope of Application

*The FAME Marketplace (Hereinafter referred to as “Marketplace”) aims to provide a federated space for embedded finance, to promote the monetization and accessibility of data. The Marketplace Terms and Conditions (hereinafter “Terms”) relate to any products, core, or non-core services, to the website, or any other element provided on the Marketplace, which *Participants* may, directly or indirectly, benefit from.*

These ‘*Terms*’ apply whenever the Marketplace is visited or used by a *Participant*. Please read these terms **carefully** before engaging in any activity on the Marketplace, as participation of any kind within the *Marketplace* is considered as an acceptance of the *Terms*.

The Marketplace reserves the right to make any changes to the ‘*Terms*’ from time to time, and without prior notice. These terms will be provided in English.

Definitions

Data assets are data products that are constructed, maintained, and made available on the Marketplace by an *Offeror*. A User can discover and freely decide to purchase these products and use them with respect to these *Terms*.

FAME Marketplace (‘Marketplace’) is an information service that *establishes a federated marketplace for Data assets, to promote the valorisation, monetisation and accessibility of data and related services. It includes all the services, products, and elements present, from time to time, on the website.*

Offeror is a *Participant* that holds the right, including the relevant Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs), to make *Data assets*, such as data sets available on the Marketplace pursuant to the ‘*Terms*.’

Offering(s) means any raw data provided in a structured or unstructured form, including *Data assets*, AI/ML models and analytical insights, other services, or product that, are available, from time to time, on the Marketplace.

Participant is an entity, individual or organisation, acting on a professional basis, which engages in the *Marketplace*, or any part thereof, in accordance with the *Terms*.

User is a *Participant* that intends to make use of the services and products available in the *Marketplace* pursuant to these *Terms*.

1. Access to the Marketplace

- 1.1 Participants can only gain access to the Marketplace upon admittance to the Marketplace, which occurs pursuant to the FAME Onboarding Procedure.
- 1.2 Any admitted applicant who participates on the Marketplace agrees to be bound by these Terms.
- 1.3 The Terms apply also to Marketplace visitors.

2. Scope of Service

- 2.1 The Offerings are made available on the Marketplace to Participants without a guarantee of continuity. The Offering should be accepted ‘as is’ and the Marketplace cannot be held responsible for any defect or lack of correspondence between the description of the Offering and its actual properties.
- 2.2 The Marketplace is federated and is set to decentralise any exchange or correspondence between the Participants.
- 2.3 A User may gain access to the Offerings in accordance with the terms set by the offeror, with reference to the Suggested Transaction Terms.

3. Subscription plan [CURRENTLY FREE TO USE]

For the duration of the FAME project, access to the Marketplace is provided free of charge.

4. Functioning of the Marketplace

- 4.1 The Marketplace aims to enhance a Participant’s experience of the Marketplace and do everything within its capacity to facilitate the findability and possibility to access Offerings on the Marketplace.
- 4.2 The Marketplace strives to ensure that the Offerings on the Marketplace are provided in a fair, transparent and non-discriminatory manner, including regarding pricing and terms of service.

5. Acceptable use policy for the Marketplace

All Participants within the Marketplace, with their best efforts, agree to refrain from and prevent others from:

- 5.1 Conducting any illegal or fraudulent activity through the Marketplace or through any content (including Offerings) made available on the Marketplace.
- 5.2 Harming, threatening, or harassing any third party.
- 5.3 Publishing offensive or abusive content.
- 5.4 Using the Marketplace for performing any illegal activity, including, but not limited to, the theft or corruption of data, damaging information systems, devices, altering software.
- 5.5 Refrain from supporting or promoting terrorism, violence or any other activity aiming at causing harm.
- 5.6 Sharing any illegal content or information, such as, but not limited to sexual abuse, minors abuse or exploitation.

6. Right to moderation content

The Marketplace retains the right to remove any content, or description thereof, that might, directly or indirectly, be deemed inappropriate, offensive, illegal, or violate the Terms, and/or the FAME Core Values.

7. Notice and Action Mechanism

- 7.1 A ‘notice and action’ system is integrated into the Marketplace to facilitate content moderation within the Marketplace.
- 7.2 Where any Participant is made aware of any content that it deems illegal or inconsistent with the Terms, they are required to submit a detailed report of the matter to the Marketplace, through the available reporting form, without undue delay.

8. Enhancement of the service

The Marketplace may use any non-personal data generated through the use of the platform for the purpose of enhancing the functioning of the Marketplace and its provision of service.

9. Representations and warranties

- 9.1 The Marketplace is provided “as is” without any express or implied warranties, including but not limited to warranties of merchantability, fitness for a particular purpose, or title.
- 9.2 The Marketplace makes no guarantee that the Platform will operate uninterrupted or error-free, or that any errors will be corrected.

- 9.3 A Participant waives all warranties and accepts that the Marketplace shall not be liable for any loss, damage, or expense, including but not limited to consequential damages, lost profits, or lost data resulting from the use or misuse of the Marketplace.
- 9.4 A Participant agrees to indemnify and hold harmless the Marketplace from any claims or damages resulting from its direct or indirect use.

10. Right to withdrawal

- 10.1 Participants, in general, hold the right to withdraw from the Marketplace at any time, pursuant to any established procedure.
- 10.2 An Offeror retains the right to withdraw from the Marketplace.
- 10.3 A User reserves the right to cancel their subscription and terminate their access to the Marketplace.
- 10.4 Any Offering made available on the Marketplace, or any data of any kind that is generated through the use of the Marketplace, will still be available to the Marketplace until activities related to security and service maintenance activities are completed.

11. Restriction of access

- 11.1 For security reasons, some or all services, including Marketplace functionalities or services related to the Offerings might be suspended at any time without prior notice.
- 11.2 For specific and imminent security reasons, any or all the Participants might be suspended from the Marketplace without prior notice.
- 11.3 The Marketplace reserves the right to restrict access to the available Offerings, temporarily or permanently, where a Participant breaches any of these Terms.

Suggested Transaction Terms

Purpose and Scope of Application

*These 'Terms' are **non-binding** and should be intended as a minimum and optional reference, whereby the transacting parties may, or may not, add, modify, or supplement all or any part of these Terms.*

The *Terms* in this document provide the general rules of engagement for the relevant parties involved in a transaction within the FAME Marketplace (hereinafter referred to as “Marketplace”). *The Transaction Terms included in this document (hereinafter referred to as “Terms”) aim to facilitate and regulate such transactions, or otherwise, the reciprocal exchange between an Offeror and User, within the Marketplace.*

Definitions

Data assets are data products that are constructed, maintained, and made available on the Marketplace by an *Offeror*. A User can discover and freely decide to purchase these products and use them with respect to these *Terms*.

Data-sharing arrangement describes a mutual agreement made by an Offeror and a User concerning the use rights of a *Data asset* made available in the Marketplace.

FAME Marketplace (‘Marketplace’) is an information service that *establishes a federated marketplace for embedded finance, to promote the valorisation, monetisation and accessibility of data and related services.*

Offering(s) means any raw data provided in a structured or unstructured form, AI/ML models and analytical insights, or any other products or services that are made available within the Marketplace.

Offeror is a *Participant* that holds the right, including the relevant Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs), to make Data assets, such as datasets, available within the Marketplace pursuant to the *Marketplace T’s & C’s*.

Participant an entity that actively engages in the *Marketplace* in accordance with the *Marketplace T’s & C’s*.

User is a *Participant* that intends to make use of the services and products available in the *Marketplace* pursuant to the *Marketplace T’s & C’s*.

1. Data assets

The Offerings made available within the Marketplace, and which concern the reciprocal exchange between an Offeror and User include:

- **Classical Data and Datasets:** Foundational data, both raw and processed, applicable across various finance scenarios.
- **Value-Added Assets:** Models, algorithms, code snippets, and software modules ready for deployment in financial applications.

- **Running Services:** Operational services that Users can integrate directly, including Energy-Efficient (EE) Analytics, AI and ML models, Situation Aware Explainability (SAX), and Explainable AI (XAI) models.

2. Permitted uses

- 2.1 Subject to a reciprocal exchange between an Offeror and a User, the latter is provided with a restricted right to use a Data asset.
- 2.2 The transferability and duration of this right shall be determined by the parties or otherwise be determined in accordance with the transaction purpose.
- 2.3 The Data asset(s), upon agreement between an Offeror and a User, may be used for:
 - Internally, for the purpose of conducting demos, research and development purposes, and related activities.
 - To develop software, data analytics or other forms and applications of automated processes, or machine learning or artificial intelligence systems.
 - To generate derived works, recommendations, and analyses, including by using models and algorithms.
 - To incorporate insubstantial portions, extracts, abstracts, or summaries of the Offerings into analyses, presentations or tools used for commercial purposes.
 - To store the Offerings in databases hosted internally or on third party hosted platforms.

3. Prohibited Uses

A Data asset purchased on the Marketplace may not be used for the following purposes:

- To conduct any illegal activities of any kind.
- To promoting terrorism, violence, or any other activity that may cause harm to another.
- The Marketplace retains the right to restrict a participants access to its services where necessary.

4. Cost and maintenance of Data assets

- 4.1 An Offeror shall bear its own costs and expenses regarding the collection, preparation, and contribution of its data to the Data asset unless otherwise agreed.

- 4.2 An Offeror is responsible for the quality, accuracy, and legality of the Offerings it contributes.
- 4.3 An Offeror agrees to provide an accurate and precise description of the Offerings it intends to make available on the Marketplace.
- 4.4 An Offeror is responsible for refining, cleaning, or expanding the Data asset as needed to ensure that it meets the appropriate specifications.

5. Privacy And Data Protection

Provided below are the options that an Offeror has regarding Data assets that may or may not contain personal data.

Anonymous data sets:

- 5.1 Option 1: An Offeror fully acknowledges that any Data asset made available on the Marketplace is understood to consist of non-personal data. In this instance, the Data asset is outside the scope of GDPR.
- 5.2 Option 2: An Offeror acknowledges that that any Data asset made available on the Marketplace may contain personal data, as defined under the GDPR. In this case, the Offeror will assume responsibility as controller pursuant to the GDPR.
 - 5.2.1 In assuming responsibility as a Controller, if a Data asset made available on the Marketplace contains any personal data, the Offeror will respect and comply with the GDPR.
 - 5.2.2 In particular, an Offeror will need to consider whether the re-use of such data is lawful, and, among other aspects, whether the purpose for which it is being processed is compatible with the previous collection purpose.
- 5.3 Option 3: [...]
- 5.4 In all cases, the Marketplace assumes no responsibility for any infringement of the GDPR. An Offeror must notify the Marketplace as soon as possible if there is a suspected or actual security breach that concerns the Marketplace or any of the available Offerings.
- 5.5 If any non-compliant activity is detected in an Offeror's account, the Marketplace is permitted to block and suspend their account to stop and mitigate the negative effects of such non-compliant activity.

6. Terms Related to The Use of Derived Material

- 6.1 Where any content contained within an Offering is copyright protected the Offeror acknowledges and agrees that the User shall retain ownership of all intellectual property rights in the derivative works, provided access has been legitimately obtained.
- 6.2 For avoidance of any doubt, in a situation where the Offering is modified only in minor ways and used for substituting the original Offering, it shall not be regarded as derived material or a work, and remains under the restrictions set out for Data assets within this agreement.
- 6.3 Where a Data asset made available by an Offeror fits the characteristic of ‘a database’ the *sui generis* right protected under article 7 of Directive 96/9/EC may be applicable.
- 6.4 The *sui generis* right protected under article 7 of Directive 96/9/EC will not apply to data generated from Marketplace activity.

7. Termination Of Contract

- 7.1 Either Party may terminate the Data-sharing arrangement immediate upon written notice if other Party is in material breach of these terms and if such breach is not cured within a reasonable period after being notified of the breach.
- 7.2 An Offeror may terminate the Data-sharing arrangement upon providing the User with a reasonable amount of prior written notice, where the Offeror’s access to material portions of the Data asset, or data in the Data asset is obstructed. In such cases the Offeror shall provide a pro-rated refund to a User for the remainder of the agreed duration for the use of the Data asset.
- 7.3 If a transaction is terminated, the access to, provision and availability of the Offering on the Marketplace will automatically be terminated without any necessary further action by either party.
- 7.4 Upon termination, the User shall destroy all copies of the Data asset(s) within their possession or control.
- 7.5 Termination shall not affect a User’s obligation to pay all fees due prior to termination, and termination shall not relieve a User of any liability for breach of these Terms.

